

D6.3 – Future Greenhouse Design Study Report

prepared for

WP 6.3 – Adaptation Towards Future Space Exploration

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Executive summary

This document details the preliminary design of a future planetary greenhouse, adapted from the Mobile Test Facility which was built and operated as part of the EDEN ISS project.

Lessons learned from the Antarctic operations phase, as well as the mission scenario for a planetary greenhouse, were considered to establish the system requirements. Based on these requirements, a preliminary design of the greenhouse structure and subsystems was developed.

The preliminary design presented in this document is a deployable cylindrical structure, with rigid end caps and an inflatable membrane shell in between. The structure has been sized to fit within the payload fairing of a Falcon 9 launcher, with a stowed configuration diameter of 4 meters and a length of 6.3 meters.

Following deployment, the structure is envisioned to be 12.9 meters long and the membrane shell will expand to a diameter of 5 meters. An estimation of the subsystem volumes was made, in order to design the internal configuration. This internal layout offers 30.8 m² of cultivation area, a more than twofold increase over the existing Mobile Test Facility.

Mass estimations were made for the different elements to determine whether or not a single launch scenario with a Falcon 9 launcher is feasible or not. The total estimated mass, with a 20% margin to account for uncertainties, was found to be lower than the launch mass capacity of the launcher.

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Acronyms

Acronym	Explanation	Acronym	Explanation
AMS	Air Management System	LEO	Low Earth Orbit
CAD	Computer Aided Design	MMOD	Micro-meteoroid and orbital debris
CDF	Concurrent Design Facility	MTF	Mobile Test Facility
CDHS	Command and Data Handling System	NDS	Nutrient Delivery System
CEF	Concurrent Engineering Facility	OSC	Orbital Sciences Corporation
CFRP	Carbon fibre reinforced polymer	PCDS	Power Control and Distribution System
ESA	European Space Agency	PCM	Pressurized Cargo Module
ESTEC	European Space Research and Technology Centre	RAID	Redundant Array of Independent Disks
FEG	Future Exploration Greenhouse	SLS	Space Launch System
IS	Illumination System	TCS	Thermal Control System

1 Introduction

1.1 General Background

After operation of the Mobile Test Facility (MTF) in the Antarctic, lessons learned were collected and incorporated into a design for space application. Lessons learned have been in the area of volume improvements, reliability, serviceability, system performance, crop yield, crew acceptance and contamination.

This report documents the activities, results and trade-offs of the workshop conducted at DLR Bremen from the 25th to 27th of March 2019. The goal was to set-up a design, which can provide at least twice as much cultivation area. During the workshop domain experts from DLR, LSG and AS were present to cover all technical and procedural aspects and create a consistent design.

1.2 Concurrent Engineering Approach

The applied Concurrent Engineering (CE) process is based on the optimization of the conventional established design process characterized by centralized and sequential engineering. Simultaneous presence of all relevant discipline specialists within one location and the utilization of a common data handling tool enable efficient communication among the set of integrated subsystems.

DLR's Concurrent Engineering Facility (CEF) in Bremen is derived from the Concurrent Design Facility (CDF) at ESA's ESTEC (European Space Research and Technology Centre), which has already been in operation for more than ten years. The CEF has one main working room where the whole design team can be assembled and each discipline is supplied with an own work station with special design tools and a common design and data model. Three screens allow display of data in front of the team. Further working positions are provided in the center of the working area and are usually reserved for customers, advisors, guests as well as the team leader. Two more splinter rooms provide the design team with separated working spaces where sub-groups can meet, discuss and interact in a more concentrated way.

The design process as applied by DLR is phased into four parts, which are described in Table 1-1.

Table 1-1: Concurrent Engineering phases as applied by DLR for studies.

Phase	Constituents	Time Frame
Initiation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Customer (internal group, scientists, industry) contacts CE team ▪ CE-team-customer negotiations: expected results definition, needed disciplines 	Weeks/ months before study
Preparation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Definition of mission objectives (with customer) ▪ Definition of mission and system requirements (with customer) ▪ Identification and selection of options (max. 3) ▪ Initial mission analysis (if applicable, e. g. based on STK) ▪ Final definition and invitation of expert ensemble, agenda definition 	Weeks before study
Study	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ K/O with presentations of key study elements (goals, requirements) ▪ Starting with first configuration approach and budget estimates (mass, power, volume, modes, ...) on subsystem level ▪ Iterations on subsystem and equipment level in several sessions (2- 4 hours each); trading of several options ▪ In between offline work: subsystem design in splinter groups ▪ Final Presentation of all disciplines / subsystems 	1 to 3 weeks in CEF
Post Processing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Collecting of Results (each S/S provides Input to book captain) ▪ Evaluation and documentation of results; transfer open issues to further project work 	Weeks to months after study

The major advantages of the Concurrent Engineering (CE)-process are:

- Very efficient regarding time, cost & results of a design activity
- Assembly of the whole design team in one room facilitates direct communication and short data transfer times
- The team members can easily track the design progress, which also increases the project identification
- Ideas and issues can be discussed in groups, which brings in new viewpoints and solutions; incl. avoidance and identification of failures and mistakes

Figure 1-1: The Concurrent Engineering Facility (CEF) during a CE-study phase at DLR Bremen.

1.3 Study Objectives

The objectives for the presented study are listed in Table 1-2.

Table 1-2: The objectives of the EDEN ISS evolution study.

Study Objectives	Description	Status
Incorporation of Lessons Learned, especially concerning system performance, crop yield, crew acceptance and contamination into the design	Technology and experience derived from WP 3, WP 4 and WP 5 will be elaborated and integrated into an advanced design and recommendations for applications to long-duration space missions.	Completed.
Derive System Technical Budgets	Create mass and volume budgets for the design	Completed.
Analyse feasibility of the design for planetary deployment	Include transfer to the planetary surface, crew, safety and risks	Completed.
A structural design shall be created with special focus on internal accommodation	The structural design shall include considerations concerning available envelope under the fairing, set-up of the module on-site.	Completed.
Create preliminary product tree	Include considerations about which components are required for subsystems and general operation of the greenhouse	Completed. A preliminary parts list has been developed and can be found in Appendix A.

2 Mission Scenario & Requirements

2.1 Mission Scenario

The mission scenario is currently not complete as no detailed plans exist for actual missions. Therefore, the current design and scenario is subject to the following assumptions:

- *In-situ infrastructure is existing:* It is assumed that before the deployment of the greenhouse, a base infrastructure is already existing at the target location (e.g. Moon or Mars), which provides power, thermal control, life-support for the crew and especially also construction tools/ robotics to set-up the regolith radiation shield.
- *Launch and transfer infrastructure is existing:* Currently, the actual launcher for human exploration missions is envisioned to be the Space Launch System (SLS), supported by commercial launchers, e.g. Falcon 9 (Space X, 2008). Due to the continued delay of SLS's development, Falcon 9 is assumed as baseline launcher for the greenhouse presented here as the launcher already exists and has flight heritage. As they share the fairing, a fitting alternative would be Falcon 9 Heavy, increasing the available launch mass to over 60 tons. Similarly, it is assumed that a (possibly re-usable) transfer vehicle will be used for transferring the module to its destination. Either this transfer vehicle or a separate system is also arranging for the landing on the respective surface. Not adding functionalities required for transfer to the greenhouse module, leads to a less complex design. For transfer the greenhouse is protected from debris and radiation with a special cover, which is shed after landing for deployment of the greenhouse module. The launch configuration along with the fairing can be seen in Figure 2-2.
- *A Docking Vehicle controls the greenhouse module attitude and position in space:* For launch and transfer it is assumed that a Docking Vehicle is attached to the greenhouse during launch, which will allow the module to become a passive target for the docking with a transfer stage, i.e. position and attitude will be controlled.

Although a detailed design of this Docking Vehicle is outside the scope of this study, some information, in particular concerning the mass, is required to assess the feasibility of a single launch mission scenario. Since, in effect, the Docking Vehicle will perform most of the functions currently carried out by cargo vehicles such as Dragon and Cygnus, it was considered reasonable to base the design on these modules.

The Cygnus module, shown in Figure 2-1, consists of a (pressurized) cargo area and a Service Module. The mass of the Service Module is 1700 kg (OSC, 2014). The pressurized cargo module can be replaced by a lightweight radiation and MMOD shield.

Figure 2-1: Enhanced Cygnus module (Credit: By NASA - <https://www.flickr.com/photos/nasa2explore/23660365065/>, Public Domain, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=45801753>)

As a first estimate, such an MMOD shield can be based on the Mars TransHab shield design. This shield has a thickness of approximately 30 cm and the areal density is estimated to be $\sim 10 \text{ kg/m}^2$, which should suffice for small to medium size particle impacts (Christiansen et al., 1999). Assuming a length of 6.6 meters and an outer diameter of 4.6 meters, as per the dimensions of the Falcon 9 payload fairing (see Figure 2-2), the weight of the MMOD shield would be around 950 kg. The combined weight of the Docking Vehicle can thus be estimated at around 2650 kg. Accounting for the uncertainty in the design with a 20% margin, the weight would be 3180 kg.

A detailed analysis of the debris environment and impact probabilities needs to be performed to determine whether or not the shield needs to be adapted to counteract larger particle impacts. Also, it may be the case that the Transfer Vehicle provides radiation and debris protection for the greenhouse after docking, in which case the Docking Vehicle might not need to provide an MMOD shield.

- *The subsystems are pre-installed in the service section of the module, further equipment is stowed in the deployable part:* To reduce the amount of work for the crew for preparation of greenhouse operations and ensure efficient usage of launches, it is foreseen that the service section of the greenhouse module requires no further fitting of subsystems after launch. Due to the expanding nature of the greenhouse section, equipment may be installed there after deployment, but the available volume is to be used for stowage as much as possible.

Based on these assumptions, the mission scenario will be (see also Figure 2-3):

1. Deployment of the module into Low Earth Orbit (LEO) via Launcher
2. Utilizing a service module, the greenhouse module is stabilized in position and attitude
3. The module is approached by the transfer vehicle, which docks with it
4. The transfer vehicle transports the module to its target location (either towards a target infrastructure in target orbit or directly to orbit)
5. A landing vehicle docks with the greenhouse module and lands it on the target surface
6. Upon landing it sheds the protection cover
7. The greenhouse module is attached to the existing habitat and covered by regolith
8. The expandable greenhouse module is deployed on the surface and extends to its full length
9. The deployed section is fitted with all remaining equipment and the plant seedlings
10. The greenhouse begins operation

The operation is intended to be modular extendable. Each greenhouse module is supposed to operate on its own, but depending on the amount of food to be created by greenhouses, several such modules can be combined with the habitat. The design presented here allows a growth area increase of more than a factor 2 compared to the EDEN ISS Mobile Test Facility, even when including, relatively, more growth area for tall plants than the FEG deployed in Antarctica.

Figure 2-2: The fairing dimensions (in meters and inches in brackets) of Falcon 9 (Space X, 2008) with the greenhouse module in the transfer configuration including the cover protecting it against debris and radiation during transfer (blue, ca. 30cm thickness) as attached to the service vehicle and the remaining volume for the s (orange).

2.2 Lessons Learned

Considering the EDEN ISS MTF as prototype for a planetary greenhouse, its operation in Antarctica at Neumeyer III station can provide relevant information about reasonable design and processes for a similar human spaceflight system. Therefore, a first step for the design work in WP 6.3 has been to collect lessons learned stemming from the Antarctica operation during EDEN ISS. These lessons have then been incorporated into design decisions and requirements alike. They are listed in Table 2-1.

The table is colour-coded concerning application during the study and category of the respective item. A green colour in the title column shows that the item has been directly transferred into the design of the study. A red colour denotes it has not been considered on purpose, whereas white colour means it has not been applicable (e.g. as it affects conditions which have to be considered during integration of the system). In the “Category” column, two options have been colour-coded: operational is marked as orange and design as blue.

To address the first two lessons a system similar to a washing machine has been introduced into the Service Section of the greenhouse module. This system can be filled with a tray for cleaning and valve cleaning. The corridor in the Service Section has been enlarged, partly by removing the working desk from the Service Section and locating it in the greenhouse section. This further allowed increasing its size. The subfloor area has been rearranged completely by placing the piping below the racks and the floor even lower for better access from the sides. This also allows for easier cleaning. The cylindrical shape of the greenhouse further allows cleaning it with water hoses and collecting the water at the lowest point. A cold porch and window do not apply for the planetary greenhouse.

The racks have been designed to be modular so the configuration can be altered during operation depending on the requirements of the space mission. The piping has been arranged in a way to prevent the formation of bubbles, requirements regard lessons 11 and 15. The Air Management System (AMS) has been enlarged, as was the Thermal Control System (TCS). A mobile ladder system, similar to a library’s, has been implemented in the planetary greenhouse.

Figure 2-3: Diagram of the mission sequence with launch, docking, transfer and landing.

Table 2-1: Lessons Learned from the EDEN ISS operation phase as collected during the study. Categories are design (blue) and operational (orange). Incorporated into the design is marked green, not considered red and not applicable is kept white in the title column.

No	Title	Category	Description
LL-001	Sink too small	design	too small for plant tray cleaning, water spillage regularly occurring => tray cleaning and checkout system transfer to station too much effort
LL-002	Plant tray cleaning has to occur in Eden Container	operational	
LL-003	Work desk too small (0.75 m ²)	design	seeding difficult (tray for seeding + container for seeds), sampling, twice the area required (possibly foldable); each week at least once seeding, sampling twice per week, cleaning of NDS tanks difficult; if possible: foldable
LL-004	80 cm corridor service section too small	design	for repairs, including second crewmember and equipment; 1 m at least, where possible increase of area (e.g. via foldable tables), opposite of subsystem access more room required (at least subsystem size + room for manipulation/ equipment)
LL-005	FEG corridor size is sufficient	design	
LL-006	Subfloor: good idea, positioning has to be reevaluated	design	if floor-plate is removed, no room for positioning, accidental stepping on pipes risky
LL-007	pipng and harness has to be rearranged for cleaning	design	"large scale"-cleaning has to be feasible
LL-008	Cold porch sizing ok	design	
LL-009	window has strong thermal effect	design	for two people sufficient, for 4 people insufficient heating through heat radiation, in winter condensation at window frame; without window uncomfortable => outside heat protection required
LL-010	modular configuration for tall growing plants advantageous	design	cucumber, tomato, peppers... not enough space without modular configuration
LL-011	metal piping would have reduced leakage	design	glued connections of current design problematic
LL-012	redesign piping to prevent leakage	design	no "U"s (for thermal, as they cause bubbles)
LL-013	water recovery of AMS too small	design	plate-heat-exchanger too small, assumptions during design insufficient, cooling liquid has to be on a lower temperature, more buffer for heat-exchanger; more water than originally anticipated has been release to atmosphere (human was not included, plants released more water, condensation)
LL-014	Thermal system too compact for access/ repairs	design	
LL-015	Equipment sizing (esp. piping/ harness) should be singular	design	especially for water recovery, change of sizing requires connectors (leakage) and introduced complex replacement situation (only one sizing)
LL-016	Height for racks difficult to work on	design	rack height for uppermost and lowest parts difficult to handle, make trays removable to work on at work table

2.3 Objectives and Requirements

As a basis for the design, a list of requirements has been established (see Table 2-2). They have been derived from generic mission objectives for a planetary habitat. Due to the increased life-time requirements in comparison to a lunar mission a Mars mission has been the baseline. Concerning requirements, similarly as stated in Section 2.1, it has been assumed that an existing infrastructure will be provided by the mission itself. Therefore, the system is not responsible for debris or radiation protection. This will be provided by the mission infrastructure, e.g. by placing the base in a cave system or erecting artificial regolith shielding.

Table 2-2: List of Mission Objectives, Mission Requirements and System Requirements for the planetary greenhouse as designed during the study (MI: Mission, SY: System, PE: Performance, DE: Design, OJ: Objective, LA: Launch, G: Goal, T: Threshold).

Mission Objectives		
No	Description	Comment
MI-OJ-0010	The mission shall allow human exploration of Mars	
MI-OJ-0020	The mission duration shall be 2 years (T) to 10 years (T)	i.e. not a short duration stay with just the landing, infrastructure is needed
Mission Requirements		
MI-DE-0010	The greenhouse system shall be launched with a single launch	
MI-DE-0020	The mission shall allow radiation and debris shielding either by location selection or artificial means (e.g. a regolith shield), independent of the greenhouse system	
System Requirements		
SY-DE-0010	The service module subsystems shall be pre-installed before launch to allow operation; only interface connection shall be required	
SY-DE-0020	The system shall fit into an envelope of 4 m in diameter and 6.6 meters length during launch	Coming from the launcher (F9 and F9H: d: 4.6 m, l. 6.6m; SLS: d: 8.4 m, l: 13 m); Diameter is limited to 4 m, to account for a 30 cm thick radiation and debris shield, as discussed in section 2.1
SY-DE-0030	The system shall have a thermal and electrical interface to the main habitat, allowing power transfer and thermal heat load transfer	
SY-DE-0040	The system shall allow resources to be transported between habitat and greenhouse, via piping and airlock tunnel; harness (for data and power)	
SY-DE-0050	The system shall be operational for 2 years without resupply	
SY-DE-0060	The launch mass shall not exceed 22.800 kg, including Service vehicle and radiation and debris shield.	s. F9 in LEO (it is assumed that a transfer vehicle will be assembled in LEO); F9H: 63.800 kg, n/ a yet
SY-DE-0070	The data rate from Mars to Earth shall not exceed 150 kbit/s; communication itself shall be enabled by the habitat	
SY-DE-0080	The level of autonomy shall be at least equal to EDEN	No research. Harvesting, seeding, etc.

	ISS	conducted by crew
SY-DE-0090	The system shall be one failure tolerant for functions relevant to keep the plants or crew alive	(e.g. NDS pumping system)
SY-DE-0100	The grow area shall contain 60% leafy plants and 40% tall growing plants	
SY-DE-0110	The system volume shall allow all required equipment to fit within	
SY-DE-0120	The system shall allow safe (contaminant free), controlled, specific grow conditions (illumination, atmosphere, humidity, nutrients) within the growth area	
SY-DE-0130	The system shall allow repair and maintenance without removal of subsystems required for operation	
SY-DE-0140	The system shall reduce debris and dirt to a minimum and allow cleaning with water with subsequent water removal	“tub”
SY-DE-0150	The atmosphere for pressuring the system shall be supplied by the habitat	
SY-DE-0160	The system shall store all elements required for nutrient delivery	
SY-DE-0170	The system shall provide fire detection and suppression	
SY-DE-0180	The system shall provide contingency equipment for breathing in case of a fire	
SY-DE-0190	The system shall have a noise level within the range of European work regulations (85 dB(A) or 137 dB(C))	
SY-DE-0200	The system shall allow connection to other modules on both ends for variable habitat configuration	
SY-DE-0210	Crew access shall be achieved by doors of at least 1.6 m height and 0.8 m width to allow safe and comfortable handling of equipment and access and egress	
SY-DE-0220	Piping shall contain no gluing to prevent leakage	
SY-DE-0230	Piping and harness diameters shall be similar among parts	To limit the amount of connectors/interfaces
SY-PE-0010	The system shall provide at least 25 m ² of grow area	At least twice as much grow area as the EDEN ISS MTF
SY-PE-0020	The system’s structure shall support its own weight and that of the installed equipment at all times	
SY-PE-0030	The system’s structure shall allow for pressure of one standard atmosphere within	
SY-PE-0040	The system shall withstand launch loads, including all pre-installed equipment, and loads during transfer and landing on the planetary surface	
SY-PE-0050	The system shall detect a rate of pressure change with > 1 mbar/ h	
SY-PE-0060	The system shall allow pressure control at a rate of 0.5 mbar/ h	
SY-PE-0070	The system shall allow proper air flow within for air supply and removal	

SY-PE-0080	The air temperature within the system shall be accurate to a set point of +/- 0.5K	
SY-PE-0090	The air temperature within the system shall be controllable between 20°C and 30°C	
SY-PE-0100	The relative humidity of the air within the system shall be accurate to a set point of +/- 1%	
SY-PE-0110	The relative humidity of the air within the system shall be controllable between 45% and 100%	
SY-PE-0120	The carbon dioxide concentration of the air within the system shall be accurate to a set point of +/- 50 ppm	
SY-PE-0130	The carbon dioxide concentration of the air within the system shall be controllable between 350 and 5000 ppm	5000 ppm was used in the EDEN ISS MTF leakage tests
SY-PE-0140	The oxygen concentration of the air within the system shall be accurate to a set point of +/- 1%	
SY-PE-0150	The oxygen concentration of the air within the system shall be controllable between 21 and 24%	
SY-PE-0160	The air flow within the system shall be accurate to a set point of +/- 0.1 m/s	TBC
SY-PE-0170	The air flow within the system shall be controllable between 0.3-0.7 m/s	TBC
SY-PE-0180	The light level within the system shall be accurate to a set point of +/- 100 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2\cdot\text{s}$	TBC
SY-PE-0190	The light level within the system shall be controllable between 0 and 1000 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2\cdot\text{s}$	TBC
SY-PE-200	The ethylene/VOC concentrations of the air within the system shall be maintained below 50 ppb	

The most relevant concern of the requirements is crew safety, i.e. fire safety equipment is mentioned in the requirements as is failure tolerance.

Another major concern of the requirements on system level is ensuring safe launch of the system, thus providing an envelope and the needed launch loads. At the same time the effort shall be reduced as much as possible, i.e. the launch shall be accomplished with a single launch. All required equipment shall be pre-installed in the service section. The default launcher assumed has been Falcon 9, which sets the fairing dimensions and launch mass. While Falcon 9 Heavy has similar fairing constraints, its planned launch mass is more than three times that of Falcon 9. However, it currently has no flight heritage and requiring Falcon 9 Heavy would also increase launch costs.

The dimensional requirements stemming from the launcher fairing could possibly be altered by application of a different fairing. However, such a fairing would need to be developed and qualified which would also increase costs. If in later phases the need for a different fairing arises a cost trade-off should be conducted to determine the best course of action, e.g. between change of fairing or separating the greenhouse into two parts with later joining on orbit.

Several requirements, e.g. SY-DE-0220, are derived from lessons learned as described in the previous section.

3 Preliminary Structure Design

3.1 Structural design description and sizing

The most common structural shapes for habitat and greenhouse designs are the dome, sphere and cylinder as these are best suited to withstand internal pressure loads, which tend to be dominant for non-terrestrial applications.

For the design study, the baseline configuration focused on a cylindrical shape, as this was most similar to the EDEN ISS Mobile Test Facility. As a result, the internal configuration of the preliminary design presented in this document could more easily be scaled and estimated based on the sizing and layout of the Mobile Test Facility. The baseline configuration is a hybrid concept composed of CLASS I and II structure elements (Kennedy, 2009), with rigid and deployable sections. This enables the greenhouse module to be stowed in a smaller volume, which can fit within the selected launcher, and deploy upon arrival on Mars in order to provide the required amount of cultivation area.

The rigid CLASS I part with aluminium shell provides a solid internal structure for installing subsystems and interfaces. The deployable CLASS II part comprises of a layered membrane system foreseeing both axial and radial expansion during deployment

The primary and secondary structures of the greenhouse have been preliminarily sized based on considerations regarding the launch system and the possibility to expand its volume both in longitudinal and radial directions. In particular, the mass and volume budgets for each of the structural elements, which are to be assembled into the full greenhouse module, were estimated based on past and present structures and concepts. The indications at system configuration level required the maximization of the available surface for the crop shelves (which could contain multiple crop trays) on a single floor level (to facilitate maintenance activities). The greenhouse has to provide at least 25 m² of cultivation area, with a 60/40 split between short and tall crops.

The greenhouse is covered by several layers of 3D printed regolith (not specified how), and all the supplies for the crops (e.g. CO₂, water, air, power) are given by the main base infrastructure. The 3D CAD model of greenhouse module in deployed configuration is depicted in Figure 3-1.

Figure 3-1: 3D CAD model of GH Module Baseline Configuration.

All the subsystems aside from the Illumination System (IS) are integrated in the rigid core of the system.

As discussed in chapter 2, the baseline launcher selected for transport into LEO is the Falcon 9. With the assumptions presented in chapter 2 regarding the service vehicle and the radiation and debris shield which need to be accommodated in the launcher payload fairing, the allowable dimensions for the stowed greenhouse module were set at a diameter of 4 meters and a maximum length of 6.6 meters.

In the stowed configuration the greenhouse has a length of about 6.3 m and a diameter of 4 m (Figure 3-2). The length of 6.3 meters was obtained from considerations of the required deployed structure length, as well as the potentially achievable packing ratio. The ratio between stowed and deployed configuration dimensions is 1:3.75 in length and 1:1.3 in diameter.

It should be noted that the packaging efficiency which can be obtained is highly uncertain. The underlying assumption is that a significant increase in packaging efficiency can be obtained over comparable systems, due to the fact that the deployable structure does not have an integrated radiation and debris shield. The resulting wall thickness is significantly lower and as such it is expected that the membrane layers can be more easily and densely packed.

Figure 3-2: GH Module Configuration and Dimensions (Stowed)

Figure 3-3 reports the configuration and dimensions of the greenhouse in the deployed configuration. The overall length of the deployed greenhouse module is 12.9 meters, with a diameter of 5 meters. A length of 3 meters is needed for the rigid Service Section, in order to accommodate all the subsystems. The underlying sizing of the subsystems is discussed in chapter 5. The deployable structure, which will provide the actual cultivation areas, has a length of 9 meters.

As the deployable structure will have a diameter of 5 meters upon deployment, and the rigid sections will retain a 4 meter diameter, it is necessary to integrate struts to support the rigid section at the desired height. For the deployable structure, to prevent damage to the membrane from debris and rocks on the surface, small air cushions are foreseen to create a small offset to the surface.

To assist with the deployment, provide additional structural integrity and to serve as mounting frame for internal equipment within the deployable section, the structure design incorporates 4 identical rigid frames (spaced 2 m apart), which also have interfaces to the membrane shell. The preliminary

design and dimensions of these frames are given in Figure 3-11. The adjacent flanges are connected by foldable longerons and floor segments.

Figure 3-3: GH Module Configuration and Dimensions (Deployed)

A description of the primary (external-facing) structure and the secondary (internal) structure is provided in the sections below, along with a brief description of a restraint cover which is foreseen for use during the transport phase.

3.1.1 Primary Structure

As mentioned, the greenhouse module has a rigid core at each end of the structure. One of these rigid cores, the primary rigid core, acts as the Service Section and houses the various subsystem components needed for the operation of the greenhouse. The other rigid core acts solely as a docking interface to other modules, to crew vehicles or suitports. In between these cores is the membrane shell and external to the cores and the membrane shell are support structure elements to position the greenhouse with respect to the surface.

Primary Rigid Core

As mentioned, the primary rigid core or Service Section has a length of 3 meters (not counting the adapter ring structure) and a diameter of 4 meters. As a preliminary design it can be based on the rigid pressurized modules which are currently used for the International Space Station. Figure 3-4 displays a CAD design of this rigid section, showing the cylindrical aluminium shell and the adapter ring structure for connection to the habitat, along with an image of the Cygnus Pressurized Cargo Module (PCM) which can serve as reference for the design.

The mass of the primary rigid core was estimated to be approximately 2000 kg, by scaling based on the dimensions compared to the Cygnus PCM reference case.

Figure 3-4: (Left) CAD model of the primary rigid core. (Right) Cygnus Pressurized Cargo Module

Secondary Rigid Core

The secondary rigid core, as briefly described, only provides a second point of egress from the greenhouse and, as such, only consists of a rigid conical section and adapter ring structure. Depending on the preferred usage, it can accommodate either a connection to another base module, to a suitport or to a rover (Figure 3-5). As for the primary rigid core, a preliminary estimation was done based on the weight of the Cygnus PCM and it was estimated to be about 500 kg.

Figure 3-5: (Left) Suitport design [credit: NASA]. (Right) Rover docking

Membrane shell

The membrane shell represents the expandable part of the module. It shall contain 1 bar pressure and protect the inner habitable volume from the outer space environment (not from micrometeorites or cosmic radiation, this protection will be done by means of 3D printed regolith cover). It is composed of several functional layers, each one providing one or more specific functions. The layers should provide a high degree of airtightness and strength and implement a smart sensor network for monitoring of the structure and environmental parameters. Figure 3-6 shows the plying of the functional layers of the membrane shell.

In the deployed configuration, the membrane shell acquires a cylindrical shape with toroidal ends. In the stowed configuration all the flexible layers are folded inside the free space available in the valleys between the internal rigid frames.

Figure 3-6: Membrane Shell Functional Layers Plying

The main structural properties are provided by the structural restraint webbing, which consists of Zylon ribbons oriented in longitudinal (meridian ribbons) and circumferential (parallel ribbons) direction. The ribbons form an interwoven net and are stitched together at crossing points and ends by a strong “Ferrari” stitching pattern. The eyelets on the ends of ribbons are connected by rings to metal bulkheads on the rigid cores, as indicated in Figure 3-7.

Figure 3-7: Detail of the junction part of the inflatable with the rigid core

The membrane shell functional layer design, along with the Zylon restraint webbing and rigid-flexible interface designs, are based on past projects, such as the project STEPS2 (*Project co-funded by EU on the "Misura Piattaforme Innovative" - Phase 2 of POR ERDF 2007/2013*). As part of this project, design and testing of packaging of a membrane shell was carried out, as shown in Figure 3-8 and Figure 3-9. The process is expected to be fairly similar for the design presented in this report.

Figure 3-8: Folding of the inflatable, as for STEPS2 project (TASI, October 2013)

Figure 3-9: Packaging and Deployment test for STEPS2

Similarly, the layer thicknesses are estimated based on previous experience. Combined with the material properties and the surface area of approximately 150 m² this enables the preliminary mass calculations for the different layers. These mass estimations are shown in Table 3-1.

Table 3-1: Membrane shell layer masses

Membrane Shell Layer	Thickness [mm]	Material	Areal Density [kg/m ²]	Mass [kg]
Internal Barrier	0,5	Kevlar Fabric	0,45	68
Air Containment Bladder	0,7	Coretech Hydroguard	0,92	138
Structural Restraint Webbing	4,2	Zylon+VITON	2,5	375
MLI (Multi-layer insulation) (20 layers)	2	Mylar/Kapton	0,2	30
External Barrier (2 layers)	1	Kevlar Fabric	0,45	135
Total	8,4	-	-	746

Supports: Legs and Pillows

In order to support the greenhouse module in its place, a system of legs and ‘pillows’ was designed to stabilise the structure along its axis and to improve thermal insulation by decreasing thermal bridges with underlying terrain.

The legs (indicated in blue in Figure 3-10) are made of aluminium and are telescopic, extending from the rigid core to rest on the planetary surface. The inflatable ‘pillows’ (indicated in yellow in Figure 3-10), 8 m in length and with a total surface area of about 11 m², will be used to support the membrane shell.

Figure 3-10: Supports for the greenhouse module structure (legs in blue, pillows in yellow)

The mass of the legs is estimated to be about 300 kg, based on past projects and concepts. For the inflatable pillows, it is assumed that they consist of an air containment bladder and an external barrier. The thicknesses and masses are indicated in Table 3-2. For two pillows, the combined mass is estimated at 30,8 kg.

Table 3-2: Pillow layer mass

PILLOWS	Thickness [mm]	Material	Density [kg/m ²]	Mass [kg]
Air Containment Bladder	0,7	Coretech Hydroguard	0,9	9,9
External Barrier (4x layers)	2	Kevlar Fabric	0,5	5,5
Total	2,7	-	-	15,4

3.1.2 Secondary Structure

Aside from the primary structure described previously, there are a number of internal structural elements which need to be implemented to allow utilization of the internal volume. These elements together make up the secondary structure of the greenhouse and consist of the rigid frames, long-erons and floor elements and shelving elements which are implemented to provide structural support for the plant cultivation trays.

Rigid Frames

The preliminary design of the rigid frames is shown in Figure 3-11. The frames can be deployed and extended along both longitudinal and radial directions, due to the telescopic geometry depicted in Figure 3-12.

Figure 3-11: Preliminary design of the rigid frame. (Left) Deployed Frame. (Right) Stowed Frame.

Figure 3-12: Telescopic geometry of the flanges

Spacers, longerons, floor elements and shelves

To obtain the desired spacing between the frames upon deployment, deployable spacers, longerons and floor elements are implemented as mentioned previously. These elements are indicated in light blue, orange and dark blue, respectively, in Figure 3-13.

For the preliminary design, the rigid elements (the frame, spacers and longerons) are all assumed to be made from aluminium. Future investigations will determine whether alternative materials would be preferable based on mass, cost or other considerations. The deployable floor elements are made from MadFlex (see Figure 3-14), which is a flexible, foldable, light and very strong material.

Similarly, the shelves (indicated in green in

Figure 3-15) will be made from MadFlex, specifically the translucent 'LUX' variant. These shelves will support the plant cultivation trays and will be placed in position after the complete deployment of the greenhouse module.

Figure 3-13: Floor panels (in dark blue), longerons (in light blue) and spacers (in orange)

MadFlex 5.5 mm HEAT RESISTANT

In order to meet the severe fire certifications of many sectors, especially aeronautic, building and transport, CoRe has developed this unique variant of the MadFlex, optimized for high temperature and flames resistance. Of course, this MadFlex still preserves its innovative mechanical features, combined with its extreme lightness and insulation ability.

	UNIT	TYPICAL VALUE	TEST
Thickness	mm	5.5	
Areal weight	kg/m ²	1.75	
Tensile strength	kN/m	500	ASTM D3039/D3039M
Failure bending moment	N·m/m	225	ASTM D7250/D7250M
Bending stiffness "rigid side"	N·m ² /m	55	ASTM D7250/D7250M
Bending stiffness "flexible side"	N·m ² /m	0.4	ASTM D7250/D7250M
Flatwise compressive strength	MPa	1.7	ASTM C365/C365M
Heat transfer coefficient	W/ m ² K	7.2	DIN52612

Maximum load for a 0,5 m x 0,5 m panel for two different restraint conditions:

OTHER FEATURES

- Produced by using components certified according to the regulation of the aeronautical sector FAR/CS 25.853 Appendix F, Part 1 (vertical burn test)
- It can continuously work up to 150°C
- A face can be easily coated by a steel layer in order to further improve the flame resistance
- A 10 m long panel can be wrapped into a 20 cm diameter
- Thermoformable in plane or curved shapes
- Good resistance to chemical agents
- Good vibration damping ability
- Great resistance to spike penetration and blade cutting

MadFlex 5 mm LUX

The MadFlex 5mm LUX variant is the perfect solution for those who need to create structures and applications with natural diffused light. The panel can also be projected in order to show thinner and brighter areas. Despite the translucency, it has great mechanical properties and an excellent insulating power.

	UNIT	TYPICAL VALUE	TEST
Thickness	mm	5	
Areal weight	kg/m ²	0.95	
Tensile strength	kN/m	400	ASTM D3039/D3039M
Failure bending moment	N·m/m	180	ASTM D7250/D7250M
Bending stiffness "rigid side"	N·m ² /m	35	ASTM D7250/D7250M
Bending stiffness "flexible side"	N·m ² /m	0.3	ASTM D7250/D7250M
Flatwise compressive strength	MPa	1.2	ASTM C365/C365M
Heat transfer coefficient	W/ m ² K	7.5	DIN52612

Maximum load for a 0,5 m x 0,5 m panel for two different restraint conditions:

OTHER FEATURES

- Thermoformable
- Super flex - 10 m rollable rollable in a diameter of 20 cm
- Excellent resistance to atmospheric and UV radiations
- Excellent resistance to chemical agents (eg hydrocarbons)
- Biocompatible
- > 100 thousand bending cycles
- Excellent vibration damping ability
- Partial elasticity that improves behavior to impulsive forces
- Extremely low environmental impact

Figure 3-14: MadFlex® properties

The shelves are composed of 3 elements: 2 supports in aluminium and the translucent MadFlex section. The aluminium supports will be designed with slots to fit in grooves in the rigid frames.

Figure 3-15: (Left) Shelves installed in the greenhouse. (Right) Stowed shelf element

The mass of the rigid frame was estimated to be 700 kg, based on the volume of material as determined from the CAD model and taking into account a density of 2800 kg/m³ for aluminium. The combined mass for the four frames then adds up to 2800 kg.

Note: No assessment was made of the loads which the frames need to withstand, so the profile dimensioning and thickness estimation was done highly conservatively.

For the spacers and longerons, the dimensions were taken to be 50 x 100 x 1900 mm, which resulted in a mass of 26,6 kg per unit. A total of 32 spacers and longerons are implemented in the preliminary design, for a total combined mass of 851,2 kg.

The mass of the floor elements and shelves was determined from the total area of the elements, along with the areal densities of the MadFlex materials. From the CAD model, the floor area was found to be 48 m², which resulted in a mass of 84 kg.

The shelves have a combined area of 47 m², for a total mass of 45 kg. The aluminium sections of the shelves are estimated conservatively to add up to another 20 kg, for a combined mass of 65 kg.

3.1.3 Restraint cover

A restraint cover is foreseen for the membrane in stowed configuration (indicated in red in Figure 3-16). The inflatable membrane will be compressed among the flanges and it could be damaged during the transport operations and the aim of the cover is to prevent this damage.

Figure 3-16: Protective restraint cover (in red) for the membrane shell for the transport phases.

The mass of the restraint cover is estimated to be 36 kg, assuming a 1 mm thick cover made of Kevlar fabric.

3.2 Options and trades

The main trade-offs performed during the study were with respect to the material selection for the membrane shell, specifically for the air containment bladder and the structural restraint webbing.

3.2.1 Membrane Material Air Containment Bladder

The main requirement for selection of the bladder material is low air permeability. Other requirements involve good mechanical properties such as puncture resistance, flexibility and tensile strength. For manufacturing purposes weldability and adhesivity are also important properties to consider.

An evaluation was made on the suitability of the following material candidates:

- EVOH (Ethylene vinyl alcohol): is the current best material for air containment but is very sensitive to humidity and has poor mechanical performance;
- PVDC (Polyvinylidene chloride): discarded for toxicity when heated or burning;
- PA-NYLON (Polyamide): lesser performance than EVOH as air barrier, good mechanical properties;
- PE (Polyethylene): lesser performance than EVOH as air barrier, good humidity barrier;
- PU (Polyurethane): lesser performance than EVOH as air barrier, good mechanical properties, good flame resistance;
- Coatings: discarded for too low efficiency in the air containment function;

To obtain the desired performance, multiple materials need to be combined. Three different configurations were investigated as indicated in Table 3-3.

Table 3-3: Candidates for the material of the bladder

Candidate 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PE / ad / PA / EVOH / PA / ad / PE (ad = adhesive polyolefin)
Candidate 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PE / PA / EVOH / PA / PE
Candidate 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PA (NYLONS) BLEND this is a monolithic film based on a blend of two miscible kinds of nylon

Candidate 1 has been selected based on past project experience (TASI, Aerosekur, ESA, 10-12 May 2011).

Structural Restraint Webbing material

The structural restraint shall be designed to withstand the operative pressure of 1 standard atmosphere with a safety factor of 4 at burst.

A trade-off (Table 3-4) and selection has been performed at fibre typology level:

- Aramid fibres: Kevlar 49 is the best compromise between cost and performance, higher mechanical properties w.r.t. Vectran HS, high decomposition temperature
- Polyethylene fibres: excluded due to very low melting point (150-170 °C);
- Liquid Crystal Polymer (LCP) fibres (Vectran HS): no advantages in its use w.r.t. Kevlar 49 due to lower mechanical properties, lower decomposition temperature, slightly higher cost;
- Rigid-rod Isotropic Crystal Polymer (Zylon PBO): best thermo-mechanical properties, highest cost among all the identified fibres.

Table 3-4: Trade-off for structural restraint webbing material

Materials	Density [g/cm ³]	Tensile Strength [GPa]	Abrasion Resistance	UV Degradation	Previous Applications	Flammability (LOI)	Ribbon Seaming Ease	Expected Lead Time	Expected Cost
Kevlar 49	1.44	3.0	Fair	High*	Yes - Flecs	28**	Easy	In-house available	Low
Technora	1.39	3.4	Fair	High* (< Kevlar)	No	25	Easy	Long	
Twaron	1.44-1.45	2.4-3.6	Fair	High*	No	29-37	Easy	Long	
Spectra 1000	0.97	3.5-4.0	Excellent	Low	No	< 20		Long	
Dyneema SK75	0.97	3.3-3.9	Excellent	Low	No	< 20		Short	
HT-Polyester (PES)	1.38		Good	Medium	NO	21		Short	
Vectran HS	1.4	2.8-3.2	Excellent	Extremely High*	Yes – ILC Dover	35			
Zylon PBO	1.56	5.8	Medium	Extremely High*	Yes - IMOD	68			High

Notes
 (*) UV protection finishing, coating, taffeta or over-braid shall be added
 (**) Kevlar 29 is fireproof

As these data originate from a variety of sources, they may be subject to deviations resulting from different test methods and/or condition

The candidates for the restraint materials configurations at fibre level are given by Zylon PBO and Kevlar 49. For the preliminary design, Zylon was selected.

3.3 Subsystem key values

For the structure, the mass is the only key values with respect to the system budgets. The masses of the different structural elements are summarized in Table 3-5 below.

Due to the level of uncertainty inherent in preliminary designs, a 20% margin is applied to the total structure mass as indicated in Table 3-5. So the total mass of the structure can be estimated at approximately 8900 kg.

Table 3-5: Preliminary structure mass

Primary Structure Elements	Mass [kg]
Primary Rigid Core	2000
Secondary Rigid Core	500
Membrane Shell	746
Support Structure - Legs	300
Support Structure - Pillows	30,8
Rigid Frames	2800
Spacers and Longerons	851,2
Floor Elements	84
Shelves	65
Restraint Cover	36
Total Structure Mass	7413
Total Structure Mass with 20% margin	8895,6

3.4 To be further studied

A significant development effort is required to progress from a preliminary design to a space-qualified structure. Some of the key aspects which need to be investigated are listed below:

- **Stowing and deployment of the primary structure**

The packaging ratio which was assumed in the preliminary design presented here needs to be analysed and verified as soon as possible using simulation tools (e.g. LS-DYNA) and (small scale) testing.

In case the envisioned stowed dimensions cannot be obtained, either the deployed structure length, and hence available cultivation area, will need to be reduced or a larger launch envelope needs to be provided to enable a single launch scenario.

The development effort needs to focus on the telescopic deployment of the flanges, as well as the packaging and deployment of the membrane shell, along with the impact of the secondary structure elements (e.g floor panels).

- **Material selection and detailed load analysis**

While some material selection has been carried out for the membrane structure of the greenhouse, the same still needs to be done for the rigid elements. A significant mass reduction may be possible if a lightweight carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) or alternative material is incorporated into the design.

Coupled with this material selection, detailed load analysis should be carried out to optimize the structure thickness and mass. As mentioned in the previous sections, the preliminary sizing was done based on existing structures and various reference concepts, or, in the case of the rigid frames and longerons, on very conservative estimates.

In some cases, the material selection process may require characterization testing to determine behaviour under, or response to, expected internal and external factors.

- **Hatch and interface design**

As the internal subsystem design develops, the interfaces to the habitat need to be clarified. These interfaces need to be integrated into the rigid structure design, while simultaneously the ability to connect to a Service Module and a Transfer Vehicle, as discussed in section 2.1, need to be implemented.

4 Preliminary Subsystem Design

This chapter contains a description of the internal layout of the Service Section and the Exploration Greenhouse and the subsystems which need to be integrated into the greenhouse in order to enable successful plant cultivation.

The preliminary system sizing and mass estimation are also presented.

4.1 Internal Layout

The Service Section contains the majority of the subsystem components which monitor and control the environmental conditions within the greenhouse and ensure optimal conditions for plant growth in the Exploration Greenhouse through atmosphere management, nutrient delivery and specific illumination settings. The Exploration Greenhouse is the actual plant cultivation area of the greenhouse module. Similar to the Future Exploration Greenhouse in the Mobile Test Facility, multiple racks are implemented in the system with a varying amount of levels depending on the crop assigned to each rack.

Due to the increased internal dimensions, compared with the Antarctic system, additional racks can be accommodated in the middle of the structure, while still providing sufficient corridor space on both sides to facilitate the crew-plant interactions.

The internal layout can be seen in Figure 4-1 through Figure 4-4 which present section views of the greenhouse module. As indicated in the images, one side of the Service Section accommodates the power control and distribution system, the main part of the command and data handling system as well as part of the nutrient delivery system. On the other side of the Service Section, the remainder of the nutrient delivery system, along with a working space and a tray cleaning area are accommodated. The atmosphere management system and the thermal control system are integrated into the top and bottom areas of the Service Section.

Figure 4-1: Section view of the Greenhouse Module

The Exploration Greenhouse contains three rack systems for plant cultivation, one on either side of the structure and one additional system in the center. The center rack system also incorporates space for crew to work or store equipment and tools. As indicated in the section views, fresh air is supplied via the supply air ducts, which inject fresh air from the sides of the structure. The warm, humid air is then collected at the top and transported to the Service Section.

Figure 4-2: Section view of the Greenhouse Module

Figure 4-3: Top view of the Greenhouse Module

Figure 4-4: Bottom view of the Greenhouse Module

4.1.1 Subsystem Descriptions

The subsystem designs are based on the as-built systems from the EDEN ISS Mobile Test Facility. For this reason, only a brief description of each subsystem is provided here, with particular focus on those aspects of the design which have been altered based on lessons learned and operational experience. For a more detailed description of the EDEN ISS MTF subsystems, please refer to the relevant subsystem design documents.

Power Control and Distribution System

The power control and distribution system consists of the main power box, an energy measurement system, cable channels and power cables, and the internal and external lighting (excluding the plant illumination system). The main power box holds all fuses, relays, wattmeters and DC converters and splits the incoming three-phase line from the habitat into lines for each subsystem, which are then split into lines to the different components.

Each subsystem has a main fuse/switch to shut down the complete subsystem and fuses/switches for each component or a group of components within the subsystem, and a main power switch is implemented to control the power for the whole greenhouse module. All subsystems except the command and data handling system and the common equipment also have a main relay to control the whole subsystem. Single relays are built in for the components which need to be controlled by the command and data handling system.

Atmosphere Management System

The AMS counteracts the deviations of the air from the nominal conditions, as a result of gas exchanges and thermal loads, by filtering and dehumidifying the air in the greenhouse. A liquid-air cooling coil is used to dehumidify air, with the recovered condensate water subsequently filtered, sterilized and pumped to the fresh water tank. A pre- and HEPA filter are implemented in the design to mitigate the risk of undesirable micro-organism growth. Additionally, a VOC filter will remove trace gases, such as ethylene, from the air to prevent a build-up which otherwise could result in adverse effects on plant and crew wellbeing.

For increased plant yield, the environment will have an elevated CO₂ level. This will be achieved via injection of CO₂ from the habitat, either via direct air exchange or via intermediate capture and storage of CO₂ in the habitat with subsequent injection in the greenhouse.

O₂ levels will be monitored, but no methods are implemented in the AMS rack to reduce the O₂ level. The baseline scenario foresees air exchange between the habitat and the greenhouse, but the possibility of oxygen capture and storage in the greenhouse will be investigated in future design phases.

Nutrient Delivery System

The overall NDS design is based on an existing hydroponic concept, developed by DLR Institute of Space Systems, which is a hybridization of classic NFT and aeroponics. The system utilizes standardized 400 x 600 x 120 mm containers (growing trays), adapted covers and high pressure misting to achieve an appropriate degree of plant water delivery and root zone oxygenation.

The main component racks, located within the Service Section contain two nutrient solution tanks with internal primary variable speed mixing pumps. Sensors include pH, EC, temperature, water level and flow rate sensors, while manual system disinfection can be achieved with an integrated ozonation system. In order to make maintenance and calibration simpler, pH and EC probes are suspended directly in the nutrient tanks. Stock nutrient reservoirs and acid/base control solutions are contained near the main tanks, with the corresponding dosing pumps mounted above the tanks. Both tanks have redundant sensors to ensure system reliability. Each nutrient tank is operated independently and can have different nutrient solution compositions that depend on experiment and plant requirements. Each nutrient tank has two separate stock supply tanks (traditionally known as A and B, but in this case the second tank will have solutions C and D available), but both are supplied from the same acid and base reservoirs for pH control.

In contrast to the MTF, which incorporated one high-pressure pump per rack, the preliminary design here foresees two larger pumps (1 active, 1 spare) for each of the nutrient tanks. These pumps will prime pressure vessels, which in turn, will be utilized for delivery of the nutrient solution to the plants. This system should reduce the number of pumps in the system, thereby reducing the number of expected component failures and, as a result, reducing the required amount of spare components and repair and maintenance work.

Return of the nutrient feed stream from the growing tray is by a combination of gravity return to a central lower reservoir and active pumping with submersible pumps which engage in response to water level sensors located within the sump reservoir. The entire NDS solution loop is closed (recirculating). Water lost to evaporation and transpiration is recovered by the condenser located in the Atmosphere Management System rack in the Service Section. Recovered water is directed to the fresh water tank located in the floor of the airlock. Additional water from the fresh water tank is injected into the nutrient tanks in response to the predetermined tank water level, or as required for nutrient composition control (i.e. lower EC).

Thermal Control System

The thermal control system consists of an active system, which uses liquid cooling loops to transport heat to the habitat. Additionally, heaters are present to ensure the temperature does not drop below 5°C (TBC) in case of subsystem failures.

The thermal control system has to actively dissipate the bulk of the heat produced inside the entire greenhouse. Specifically, the thermal system will dissipate the heat from the AMS and the LED panels. The AMS thermal loop and the LED thermal loop have a similar architecture. A pump with an expansion vessel forces a coolant liquid through the system (AMS dehumidifier or LED cold plate) and then towards a plate heat exchanger.

Temperature regulation of the thermal loops will be done by mixing the in- and backflows using three-way valves. For the AMS cooling coil, the volume flow will also be controlled via three-way valve, whereas for the LED panels flow regulation valves will manage the flow rate through the sys-

tem. The transport architecture handles the opposite side of the two heat exchangers, supplying a cold coolant liquid and transporting the ‘hot’ coolant liquid to the habitat, with a pump and expansion vessel ensuring the desired flow rate is met and sensors providing the required data for control of the actuators.

Control and Data Handling System

The baseline control and monitoring system design consists of two PCs connected over an Ethernet switch to the network. The two CDHS PCs located within the Service Section are the Main Control Server PC and the Camera Control PC.

The Main Control Server PC, including RAID system, is used to control and monitor all systems inside and outside the greenhouse, the safety system, and the camera system. It can also be used to visualize the control parameters on the connected screens located in the Service Section, to write or upload new program code to the control system and to download and store control data. The Camera Control PC is dedicated to processing camera images and buffering control data.

Aside from the command and data handling, and the communication components, the CDHS also comprises a safety system to ensure crew safety. This system, consisting of O₂, CO₂ and smoke sensors provides visual and audio cues within the greenhouse and relevant information is transmitted to the habitat and the control room on Earth.

Illumination System

The Illumination System consists of the LED panels which shall be installed in the Exploration Greenhouse. For initial sizing, the same setup is used as in the MTF, with one water-cooled LED panel per tray. For future development work, a more detailed consideration will be made regarding the use of water-cooled versus air-cooled LED units.

4.2 System sizing/analyses

For system sizing concerning their volume, resp. area, the baseline has been the FEG. To determine system sizes, a scaling factor has been estimated for a growth area increase of factor 2. The basic assumption has been that the available height has been 2.2 m as for the EDEN ISS MTF. Depending on the exact system, different scaling factors have been set. The summary of this is shown in Table 4-1.

Table 4-1: Calculation of sizing based on an assumed increase of factor 2 for the growth area and scaled to the actually designed growth area of 30.8 m². The last row shows the calculated volume gradient, the actual growth area of the design, the original volume of the FEG and the subsequent total subsystem volume for the presented design. The last column shows the individual proportions based on the respective factor.

System	EDEN ISS [m ²]	Factor for doubled growth area	Area [m ²] for doubled growth area	Actual Volume [m ³]
Nutrient Delivery System (NDS)	0.9	1.5	1.35	4.52
Air Management System (AMS)	0.9	2	1.8	6.02
Thermal Control System (TCS)	0.48	1.5	0.72	2.41
Power Control and Distribution System (PCDS)	0.4	1	0.4	1.34
Command and Data Handling System (CDHS)	0.2	1	0.2	0.67
Total	2.88		4.47	

	Growth Area [m ²]	EDEN ISS Value
System Volume:	0.27984	30.8
		6.336
		14.96

As a similar height is available for all subsystem volumes, only areas are calculated. Therefore, actual areas for each subsystem can be calculated, which are shown in the fourth column. From the totals in the last but one row, a gradient can be calculated, which is presented in the second column of the last row. Together with the actual growth area of the design, shown in the next column, this provides the volume in the following manner:

$$V = m \cdot A + b \quad (4-1)$$

Here, V is the volume, m the gradient (0.27984), A the actual growth area (30.8 m²) and b the ordinate stemming from the original design, here the subsystem volume of the MTF (6.336 m³). To receive the actual volume of the respective subsystem, the area (as the height is similar) is taken into account. The subsystem's area for the doubled growth area is related to the total area of all subsystems, thus receiving their ratio of the volume.

This was then considered for the actual design, fitting these volumes into the Service Section of the greenhouse module.

For the calculations the following assumptions have been made:

- 1) The internal diameter of the Service Section is 4 m
- 2) The internal diameter of the greenhouse, deployed, is 5 m
- 3) A corridor of 1.2 m is available for traverse in the Service Section

The mass budget was established based on an extensive parts list which was established for each subsystem based on the existing MTF design and the changes which were implemented based on lessons learned. The full parts list, along with mass estimates can be found in Appendix A.

4.3 Subsystem key values

Table 4-2 shows the mass estimates for the different subsystems integrated in the greenhouse module. The corresponding parts list can be found in Appendix A as mentioned. As comparison, the masses of the subsystems from the EDEN ISS MTF are presented as well.

Table 4-2: Key values of the greenhouse module subsystems.

	Estimated Mass [kg]	Actual EDEN ISS MTF [kg]
Structure*	760	-
AMS	884	912
NDS	766	849
TCS	990	405
IS	900	352
CDHS	691	477
PCDS	680	533
Other/Misc.**	65	160
TOTAL	5736	3688

* For the EDEN ISS MTF, the structure mass is included in the different subsystem masses.

** For the EDEN ISS MTF, the miscellaneous components include tools and consumables.

4.4 To be further studied

All of the subsystem designs require further development efforts in order to obtain a system which can be qualified for space missions. However, some key aspects have a higher level of uncertainty and as such need to be prioritized in future project phases.

- **Gas Exchange System**

The integration of a greenhouse into the life support system of a habitat, or planetary base, can provide significant benefits but also comes with a number of challenges. In particular, the air exchange between the habitat and the greenhouse, in order to optimally benefit from the natural processes of plants, is something which needs to be studied in further detail.

In previous design studies the possibility of periodic direct air exchange between the habitat and the greenhouse was considered, where oxygen-rich air is vented to the habitat and CO₂-rich air is provided to the greenhouse. An alternative to such a system could be the implementation of CO₂ and O₂ capture and storage systems, with dedicated supply systems transporting the captured gases to the desired location.

A detailed trade-off needs to be done on the different options as early in the design process as possible.

- **Nutrient Delivery System**

The nutrient delivery system with pressurized tanks instead of dedicated pumps as proposed here has not been tested yet in the EDEN ISS Mobile Test Facility or in the laboratories of the project partners. A test system should be developed as soon as possible to determine whether or not the expected benefits occur or not and to assess potential unforeseen disadvantages and operational challenges.

The results of this test should be used to review the nutrient delivery system design.

5 Summary and Conclusion

A preliminary design of a greenhouse module for future crewed Mars missions has been developed. Based on lessons learned from the Antarctic operations phase of the Mobile Test Facility, as well as an initial mission scenario concept, assumptions and requirements were defined which drove the greenhouse module design. The lessons learned were furthermore implemented in the design of the greenhouse subsystems, with an aim towards more reliable, efficient and effective performance.

Following an evaluation of common structure concepts, a preliminary structural design was developed for a hybrid cylindrical deployable module. The primary structure consists of a deployable membrane structure with a rigid section on both ends. The structure expands in both the longitudinal and radial direction upon deployment and is supported by a number of rigid flanges which can be deployed telescopically. The stowed structure is designed to fit in an envelope with diameter of 4 meters and a length of 6.3 meters, and upon deployment, the total length will increase to 12 meters and the membrane shell will expand to a diameter of 5 meters.

An initial evaluation of the subsystem volumes was carried out to determine the feasibility of fitting all components within the stowed greenhouse for a single launch scenario. Based on this evaluation and the developed configuration, this appears to be possible. Similarly, the masses of the different elements were evaluated to determine whether or not it would be possible to launch with a single Falcon 9 Launcher. The mass budget is presented in Table 5-1 indicates that, even with a 20% margin to account for the uncertainties in the design, the total mass is below the maximum payload mass of the Falcon 9 Launcher (22800 kg).

Table 5-1: Mass budget overview

	Mass
Docking Vehicle	2650
Structure *	8173
AMS	884
NDS	766
TCS	990
IS	900
CDHS	691
PCDS	680
Other/Misc.	65
TOTAL	15799
TOTAL w/ 20% Margin	18958,8

* The Structure mass consists of the structure element masses presented in chapter 4, along with the estimated masses for additional internal structural elements as listed in Appendix A.

The feasibility of a single launch scenario also depends heavily on the ability to package the greenhouse module in the available payload envelope. The packaging and deployment of the greenhouse module needs to be assessed via simulation methods and (small-scale) testing. Additionally, the assumptions regarding the Service Vehicle need to be verified through a detailed design process.

The preliminary design presented in this document would provide 30.8 m² of cultivation area, of which 60% is assigned to short crops (e.g. lettuce, herbs) and the remainder is utilized for tall crops such as tomatoes and cucumbers. Based on lessons learned from the Antarctic operations phase, this should provide sufficient supplement fresh food for a crew of 6-10 and could already begin to contribute to some percentage of crew caloric intake.

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Appendix A Component List

Element/Component	Qty	Mass per element (kg)	Total mass (kg)	Dimensions per element (mm) (L x W x H)
SERVICE SECTION				
Nutrient Delivery System				
Bulk Solution Tanks	2	30	60	400 L
Stock Solution Tanks	4	1	4	30 L
Acid / Base Tanks	2	1	2	15 L
Micropumps & Conditioning Unit (Sensors, valves)	2	50	100	
Pressurized Tanks	4	20	80	0,03 m ³
High pressure pump	2	30	60	30x30x40 ?
Piping - SES	1	60	60	
Mixing & Distribution Unit - incl. Valves	2	20	40	
Fresh Water / Waste Water Tanks	2	15	30	200 L
Habitat I/F	1	20	20	
Misc				
Dishwasher / Tray Cleaning & Check System	1	50	50	
General lighting	3	2,5	7,5	
Power System				
Power Box	1	530	530	
Power Harness	1	50	50	
Command and Data Handling				
ARGUS Box	1	480	480	
Server PC	2	5	10	
Screens	2	3	6	
Safety System (Co2, O2, fire detection and suppression)	1	25	25	
Communication System (WLAN, VOIP, Routers, Switches)	1	25	25	
Data Harness	1	30	30	
Thermal Management System				
Pressure Vessels / Accumulators	2	60	120	
Heat Exchanger	2	40	80	
Pumps (2 redundant)	4	10	40	
Piping	1	200	200	
Three way valves & actuators	2	10	20	
Hydraulic separator	1	30	30	
Atmosphere Management System				
Fans (with casing)	4	20	80	
Cooling Coil w/ basin (special anti-microbial coating)	1	300	300	
Heaters	1	30	30	
Filters & Casing	1	100	100	
Ducting	1	150	150	
Habitat Exchange System (w/ Valves & filters)	1	50	50	
Service Section air conditioning	1	50	50	

Structure				
Floor	1	40	40	
Ceiling	1	40	40	
Wall	2	40	80	
Subsystem Structure support	1	300	300	
Nutrient Delivery System				
Trays w/ Lids / Misters	90	1	90	
Piping	1	200	200	
Return pumps	1	20	20	
Atmosphere Management System				
Ducting – Flexible	1	30	30	
Circulation Fans	50	1	50	
Sensors	1	20	20	
Flow Regulators	8	3	24	
Thermal System				
Piping & Valves & Accessories	1	500	500	
Illumination System				
LED lamps & ballast	90	10	900	
Power System				
Power Harness	1	100	100	
Command and Data Handling				
Data Harness	1	70	70	
Plant Health Monitoring Cameras	10	2	20	
Safety System	1	25	25	
Misc				
General Lighting	3	2,5	7,5	
Structure				
Subsystem structure support	1	300	300	
		Mass (MTF)		
		Subtotal	5736,0	
		Margin	20	
		Grand total	6883,2	